

THE POWER OF BEING AN EDUCATED INDIVIDUAL

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Annotation: This article provides information about how a person to be a educated individual and its power. Education makes a person productive, allowing him or her to contribute to society in a positive way. A well-educated individual understands how to act in a polite and non-offensive manner.

Key words: educated person, individual, society.

The value of education at a much younger age. Our first tryst with learning begins at home, and our first teachers are our parents, grandparents, and often siblings. The importance of education lies in its continuity, learning is a lifetime process that will stop with our death. It is the foundation for the development of a healthy individual and society. Our world cannot have a bright future if our culture lacks education. Education is the key to change. It is an important tool that allows a person to understand his or her rights and responsibilities to his or her family, society, and nation. It improves a person's ability to view the world and to fight against misdoings such as injustice, corruption, and violence, among other things.

Education is meant to hone talent, sharpen our mindsets and educate us on a myriad of things. In school, we cover a variety of topics such as history, arithmetic, geography, politics, and so on. These subjects sharpen children's minds and allow the kid to absorb knowledge from all subjects, and his or her mental level is increased. Here are some cognitive benefits of learning and education that ensure growth and development in children:

Stability. Education's importance in our lives provides us with stability in our everyday lives. Everything may be split, but not your education, you must be told. You can improve your chances of getting a better job with the aid of your degree and expertise.

Financial Security. Our financial stability is helped by education. Higher-qualified individuals receive higher-paying employment in this era, allowing them to guarantee their future.

Self-dependency. Education teaches us to be self-sufficient in our daily lives. A person's education is his alone, and with it, he may feel safe and self-sufficient.

Equality. Equality is a right that everyone deserves. If everyone had the opportunity to pursue higher education, there would be a greater likelihood that

everyone would earn a large sum of money, and there would be fewer disparities across social classes. It aids in the pursuit of equality.

Confidence. Confidence is one of the finest aspects of success. Education boosts a person's self-assurance. You can go further into a topic that you are already familiar with. With the information you've obtained through your schooling, you can converse about that issue far better than others.

Knowledge and education is power. Education enables individuals. Enables them to innovate, understand, adapt, and overcome. Everything we learn helps us in life in one way or the other. It helps make our life convenient and easy. Good education is basically the knowledge that gives people perspective and information about things which can range from being as simple as fixing a water pipe to building a rocket destined for moon. When we are educated, we can adapt to each and every aspect of life better and it also helps us overcome many hurdle of life and gives perspective about a lot things such as finance, planning, etc. All this can make any individual feel powerful because there remains nothing in life that they cannot tackle.

The power of education is invaluable — it broadens human's minds, significantly enhances perspectives, changes attitude towards life and shapes all society. In today's uncertain world only one thing may be sure — no one can take this knowledge away from us. It is a secret weapon that we always carry with us and that we can use to our advantage. Education is vital to one's success in life. It is essential for an individual's entire growth. The process of learning and improving one's skills is referred to as education. Wisdom and the ability to handle challenges come with knowledge. Education enhances one's quality of life while also granting social recognition. Though education is essential for everyone, the need for it is most acute during childhood. Education is a valuable tool for gaining learning and wisdom. Though books are essential to education, the notion encompasses more than just books and bookish knowledge. It isn't required for education to be only based on books. The most important goal of education is to help people with how to read and write. The first step toward literacy is reading and writing. Education provides a person with endless opportunities for growth and advancement. People who have had an education tend to be more calm and self-assured. People who have been educated are disciplined and understand the importance of time. Education allows a person to be more expressive and opinionated. H/She was able to readily communicate his/her viewpoints, which were supported by a clear aim and rationale.

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